

Final report on communication and dissemination activities.

WP8 – Deliverable 8.4

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in
the plastic packaging value chain

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From March 2017 to June 2020

Prepared by: ICLEI EURO

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Approvals

Author/s	ICLEI EURO
Task Leader	ICLEI EURO
WP Leader	ICLEI EURO
Reviewer(s)	CIRCE

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA: Consortium Agreement
CDP: Communication and Dissemination Plan
EC: European Commission
SME: Small and Medium Enterprise
NGO: Non-Governmental Organization
WP: Work Package
T.X.X: Task
D.X.X: Deliverable

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

CIRCE: FUNDACION CIRCE – RESEARCH CENTRE FOR ENERGY RESOURCES AND CONSUMPTION
AITIIP: FUNDACION AITIIP
NOVAMONT: NOVAMONT SPA
MATER: MATER-BIOTECH SPA
MBP: MATER-BIOPOLYMER SRL
BUMAGA BV: BUMAGA BV
TECNOPACKAGING: NUEVAS TECNOLOGIAS PARA EL DESARROLLO DE PACKAGING Y PRODUCTOS AGROALIMENTARIOS CON COMPONENTE PLASTICA SL
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FATER: Fater S.p.A.
CRF: CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA
UNE: ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE NORMALIZACION
RINA-C: RINA CONSULTING
EKODENGE: EKODENGE MUHENDISLIK MIMARLIK DANISMANLIK TICARET ANONIM SIRKETI
ECOEMBES: ECOEMBALAJES ESPANA, S.A.
CITY OF RIJEKA: GRAD RIJEKA-GRADSKO VIJECE
KARTALMUN: KARTAL BELEDIYE BASKANLIGI
CALAF IND: CALAF TECHNIQUES INDUSTRIALS SL
OCU EDICIONES: OCU EDICIONES SA
ICLEI EURO: ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
PLASTIPOLIS: PLASTIPOLIS

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SUMMARY

The final report on communication and dissemination activities explains how communication and dissemination activities were undertaken throughout the CIRC-PACK project to share its results and achievements with the wider circular plastics community and the general public.

This deliverable provides an analysis of the communication activities, present specific cases and challenges, and summarises how the CIRC-PACK consortium positioned its work in the wider context of the European Union's commitment to a circular economy for plastics. The deliverable uses information provided by partners on various communication activities as well as monitoring and tracking conducted by ICLEI EURO. In total, it provides an overview of the actions executed in terms of communications to reach the key objectives for Work Package 8 (WP8).

In addition, it provides a retrospective look on the original communications plan – updated twice in the project period – to allow future projects working within the circular economy for plastics to benefit from the key lessons learnt and other insights. It reviews how key stakeholder groups were reached and what channels were most appropriate for the different audiences.

The aim of this final report is to provide a reference point for the overall implementation of WP8 in the CIRC-PACK project.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project background

The EU **Circular Economy Package** adopted in 2015 aimed to stimulate Europe's transition towards a circular economy through measures that would cut resource use, reduce waste and greenhouse gas emissions, boost recycling, and eventually foster energy savings, enhancing global competitiveness – as well as sustainable economic growth – and generating new jobs, in line with EU strategic objectives. The Package consisted of an [EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy](#) and an [annex to the action plan](#) that set out the timeline for when the actions would be completed¹.

The plan (which has since been updated to as part of the European Green Deal²) was, in its very essence, the background for the CIRC-PACK project and, therefore, also for the communication efforts of the project.

It was in this framework, and to contribute to the above-mentioned targets, that CIRC-PACK set the ambitious objectives of creating, testing and validating alternative bio-based, biodegradable and compostable, and recyclable plastics for multiple purposes, as well as new types of multilayer and multi-material packaging that can be easily recycled, which is expected to increase recovery rates and quality while reducing the amount of waste sent to landfills. This was done through a systemic approach and large scale demonstrations that encompassed value and supply chains in their entirety and engaged all actors involved³, as well as proposing new business models and regulation best practices.

1.2 Communication background

The CIRC-PACK communication activities performed in the project were based on the plans put forward in the original Grant Agreement and included in Deliverable 8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP). This plan laid the foundation for the project communication, and covered a wide range of issues. The overall Work Package 8 included three tasks covering a strategy (Task 8.1), materials (Task 8.2) and actions (Task 8.3).

The most important aspects of the CDP are summarised in the following sub-sections and the report as a whole will share how these aspects were addressed to communicate effectively about the CIRC-PACK project.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

³ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/circ-01-2016-2017.html>

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1.2.1 Objectives

Awareness, communication and dissemination actions targeting specific audiences with tailored messages were noted as key to the success of CIRC-PACK from the very beginning. An early resource mapping exercise, in which all CIRC-PACK partners took part, was used to produce a communications strategy in 2017 (Deliverable 8.1) which was updated in 2018 and 2019. It included a wide range of specific goals, target groups and actions to be taken, and framed the overall general communication objective in the following way: widely spread CIRC-PACK results among the main target audiences identified in WP2 and WP7, raising awareness about the project's technical, environmental, social and economic benefits.

In order to achieve this main objective, WP8 planned to pursue three specific objectives:

1. Define an agile communication strategy adapted to the different target groups and messages.
2. Prepare a corporate image pack and a set of materials for the promotion and the comprehensive dissemination of the project and its outcomes.
3. Execute and monitor the Communication and Dissemination Plan with continuous engagement with the main target groups and tailored messages while measuring, controlling, managing and quickly adapting the strategy, if needed.

1.2.2 Messages and target groups

From the outset of the project, **key messages were defined** to be put forward by partners, by WP8 and on all CIRC-PACK platforms. These key messages were:

- Resources are limited and increasingly expensive. We need to be smart and sustainable about their use, adopting a new sustainable model based on reuse-repair-recycle approach.
- Our production and consumption patterns affect resource stocks and generate waste, which too often ends up in landfill. Reinventing plastics for the circular economy and addressing their life cycle is one solution way to address this problem.
- CIRC-PACK sees plastic waste as a valuable resource that should re-enter the value chain.
- CIRC-PACK will develop and validate bio-based, compostable and recyclable plastics, plus eco-friendly multilayer / multi-material packaging, and enhance recycling technologies.
- CIRC-PACK believes that recycling rates in Europe and the quality of recovered materials can be improved to develop secondary raw materials for different purposes.
- Creating an enabling business and regulatory environment is crucial to market uptake of the proposed innovations for resource efficiency and waste management.

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In addition to the general key messages, tailored messages⁴ were defined for each important target group using input from the consortium. The specific tailored messages can be found the original CDP, and the specific target groups chosen for CIRC-PACK were the following:

- Public authorities and regulators
- Value chain actors – private sector
- The scientific community
- Waste/recycling companies
- Consumers
- Potential investors

1.2.3 Channels

The CIRC-PACK project used a wide range of different channels to achieve its objectives, reach the target groups and deliver the key messages from the project. These channels were chosen before the project started, and included the following:

- Project website and newsletter
- Social Media - LinkedIn and Twitter
- Project e-mail
- Leaflets, posters and banner
- Events
- Scientific publications
- Media and press releases
- Project videos
- Partner Channels

1.2.4 Key performance indicators

As part of the clear roadmap that was presented in the CDP (D8.1), Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were listed to assess the development in the projects and monitor progress. It would also allow partners to process results, mitigate risks and correct deviations in the plan if those were to occur. One KPI, on ‘media mentions’ was lowered from 20 press mentions per year to 5 in an update to the plan. With results of the project coming in late, it did not seem beneficial to aim for 20 press mentions in the early years. Regardless of the changed KPI, 20 press mentions were achieved in the final year as originally sought.

The **KPIs for CIRC-PACK’s communication activities** were:

⁴ For a full list of the specific messages see Deliverable 8.1.

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Table 1: Communication and dissemination indicators for evaluation as seen in the original CDP Plan from M6

Minimum targets to be achieved by the end of the project					
Website	Newsletter	Social media	Videos	Events	Media actions
2,000 unique visitors over the course of the project	200 subscribers	200 total followers for Twitter and LinkedIn	1,000 total views	20 participants in each workshop and 50 in the conference	5 press releases in total, and at least 20* press mentions per year

The set of KPIs will, together with the overall objectives and the overview of channels, be used to explain and evaluate the various CIRC-PACK communication and dissemination activities in this report.

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2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND CHANNELS

2.1 Project website and newsletter

Throughout the project, the CIRC-PACK **website** experienced a steady increase in usage and averaged 1,200 unique monthly visitors between April 2019 and April 2020. The website was designed to be easily approachable with a simple build up and an uncomplicated site map.

Picture 1: Screenshot from Circpack.eu

Since the launch of the news section on CIRC-PACK.eu, 38 news stories have been published covering topics specifically related to CIRC-PACK, such as conference participation, new videos or results from the project, but also covering central themes for the wider circular economy – with stories on the European Green Deal in relation to plastics etc.

The website, in addition to the news, also contains a factsheet page for each solutions – with a video, key facts and links to the publishable summaries of the reports related to the solutions.

Generally speaking, the numbers of visitors to the website has been steadily rising, while the total amount of downloaded material (reports and other documents) have increased significantly over the final months of the project. This aligns with the expectation that the project in the most mature phase would have the most relevant content to share.

Figure 1: Unique visitors to the CIRC-PACK website

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Figure 2: Downloads from the CIRC-PACK website.

In sum, the website served its function as a place for interested parties to find more information related to CIRC-PACK. It now contains an online library of CIRC-PACK information for anyone to browse and it will be kept alive for at least two years following the end of the project.

The original aim of reaching 2,000 unique visitors over the course of the project was reached much quicker than anticipated and as figure 1 explains, this was even the case for a single month on its own (March 2020).

The **newsletter** received a total of 132 subscribers and following the final webinar, 93 participants were added to allow for sending all the expected and promised material meaning the final event newsletter was shared with a total of 225 compared people. Although the number of subscribers might not seem too high, main explanation is that the project has been strongly followed on Twitter (see 2.2) – so, many people opted to receive more frequent news on the project and on topic-related news by becoming a follower of the CIRC-PACK Twitter handle or through the often-visited website, rather than subscribing to the newsletter (also considered a less interactive way of receiving and consuming information). A newsletter archive is also available on the website (<https://circpack.eu/news/>), so people who are not subscribers to the newsletter also have access to the different issues.

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2.2 Social Media - LinkedIn and Twitter

The Social media profiles of CIRC-PACK have been a Twitter handle and a Group on LinkedIn as planned in the original communications strategy. Both accounts have been shared with another European plastics packaging project from the same call – the PlastiCircle project. This was also planned in the Communications Strategy and agreed with the European Commission. From the onset, the goal was to receive 200 followers for each.

Picture 2: Screenshot of the most popular post in the LinkedIn Group

The **LinkedIn Group** reached the goal and as of May 2020 has more than 350 members. The LinkedIn group has been mainly used as a one-way communication channel, in which CIRC-PACK partners have posted information to the group. Furthermore, some non-CIRC-PACK people have also posted relevant information.

On **Twitter**, the stated goal of 200 followers in the Communications Strategy was met many times over, and the impact was clearly proven.

With a follower count of 1,791 (end May, 2020) the Twitter account @CIRC_Economy has attracted quite an audience. Here, perhaps more than on LinkedIn, the symbiotic relationship

between PlastiCircle and CIRC-PACK helped both projects to gain increased traction on Social Media and worked well throughout the project.

As an example, the period surrounding the EU Green Week in May 2019 was the most successful on Twitter with a total number of monthly impressions reaching near 100,000 for three months straight. A physical event was hosted by PlastiCircle, which included a strong CIRC-PACK presence on the Twitter channels and, at the event, more than 20 partners joined for CIRC-PACK workshop. One tweet related to the event, and presenting the CIRC-PACK project alone reached 4,800 impressions, and similar numbers were repeated on CIRC-PACK's work in the period.

In total, @CIRC_Economy on Twitter averaged 34,000 impressions in the final two years of the project and tweeted a total of 725 times including re-tweets. This averages roughly 30 tweets per month with activities varying from month to month in the period.

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Picture 3: Screenshots - Left: Tweet about CIRC-PACK in relation to the Circular Cities Event in May 2019 (4.800 impressions). Right: Most popular CIRC-PACK tweet from December 2019 (12.000 impressions)

CIRC-PACK also benefitted from wider cooperation with projects on Social media, where the projects involved in the Plastics Circularity Multiplier were likely to retweet and share important and interesting announcements.

To conclude on the Social Media activities, they were overall successful with the biggest impact made on Twitter. Changing algorithms on LinkedIn in the period leads to the conclusion, that a group is no longer the most effective means of communication for a project such as CIRC-PACK. Twitter, as described before, worked well to reach the community with many engaged users from the European Circularity movement sharing content. As proven by the total numbers for CIRC-PACK, people were reached well on Social Media.

Figure 3: Impressions on the Twitter account @CIRC_economy

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information collected for the final brochure was also used to produce factsheets for each demo case to be shared on the CIRC-PACK website.

Picture 6: Final CIRC-PACK brochure.

2.5 Events

Throughout the period, partners reported taking part in no less than 131 different events. The activities varied from presentations at scientific conferences, to participation in large exhibitions (See picture 5) to CIRC-PACK arranging workshop or online events.

The most active partner in terms of events was the Municipality Kartal in Turkey that took part in regular public activities to encourage and inform local citizens about zero-waste and the Municipality's work in CIRC-PACK. In total, the CIRC-PACK team participated in more than 40 such activities which were also described by local media in an article in the local press⁵.

⁵ Local press article on Kartal's engagement in CIRC-PACK: <https://www.timeturk.com/kartal-belediyesi-cevre-koruma-ve-kontrol-mudurlugu-nden-plastik-donusumu-icin-onemli-adim/haber-1150107>

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The different CIRC-PACK events reported by partners

Total events reported: 131

- Events - oral presentation at public event
- Events - organisation of conference
- Exhibition
- Events - oral presentation at scientific event
- Events - organisation of workshop

Figure 4: Events reported by partners in the CIRC-PACK monitoring tool.

The event participation in CIRC-PACK was also focused on a series of workshops, with partners reporting organising a total of 16 workshops. This number includes intensive and large workshops dedicated to CIRC-PACK at Spain's National Environmental Congress, as done by CIRCE and OCU in 2018⁶, or a small session with a group of like-minded industry-colleagues, as arranged by partner BUMAGA in the Netherlands several times in 2018. 6 of these workshops were organised with or by OCU as part of Work Package 7. These workshops were well attended and generally reached the KPI of 20 participants with some having substantially more participants.

2.6 Final event (Final Webinar)

The final event of CIRC-PACK was scheduled to take place in Brussels on March 17, 2020, and had 85 registered participants on March 6, when it was quickly becoming clear that the COVID-19 crisis would make the completion of the event impossible. Up until that point, plans had been made for some partners who might not be able to travel, but the project was still planning to push through with what was scheduled as a "Breakfast at Sustainability's" by ICLEI Europe – the event is a recurring series in Brussels, location had been found, catering ordered, etc.

However, as the event was made impossible – both by the Belgian authorities and practical limitations on travel for partners, with no foreseeable change in sight – the decision was

⁶ Watch the video from the workshop here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2bjb8cxjtNo>

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taken, in agreement with the European Commission to, instead, move the event online. This was announced to all the original registrants through emails and partners and social media helped spread the news about the event taking place online.

The Final Webinar took place on March 17 and followed the original plans for the event, though in a shorter format. Speakers were Mr. Paul Lemos from the European Commission, as well as Demo Case Leaders, Project Coordinator and OCU sharing the experience with consumer testing of the CIRC-PACK products.

Webinar: Innovations in plastics for a circular economy

<p style="text-align: center;"><i>10.00</i> Welcome and introduction - Ruud Schuthof, ICLEI</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>10.05</i> European strategy for plastics in a circular Economy - Paulo Lemos, European Commission</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>10.20</i> Plastics from renewable resources - Alessandro Delicio, NOVAMONT:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Eco-friendly packaging design Henrike Holwerda, BUMAGA</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Enhanced sorting and recycling - Julio Vidal, AITIIP:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>10.50</i> Social acceptance of the CIRC-PACK packaging - Belén Ramos, OCU</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>11.00</i> Environmental assessment Aitana Saez De Guinoa Vilaplana, CIRCE</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>11.10</i> Final Remarks</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>11.15</i> End of webinar with a possibility for Q&A</p>
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Picture 7: Programme for the Final Webinar

The webinar started off well and a total of 116 participants joined the session and enjoyed interesting presentations from the European Commission, and the first group of CIRC-PACK partners. At around 10.50 however, disruptions began due to a problem by Webex (the platform used for the webinar), that initially affected the audio and video-feed for some participants, including the moderator, and then later spread to more. Halfway through the presentation from Belén Ramos of OCU, the connection was cut for almost everyone in the webinar. Following a frantic attempt to re-start unsuccessfully, the decision was taken to stop the webinar and inform the participants that they would receive the final presentations as a recording later.

The investigation into the disruptions were inconclusive, but it appears CISCO WEBEX had cluster issues in Germany on the day. March 17 was the first full day of the lockdown in Germany, which could be an explanation.

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Regardless, the CIRC-PACK partners re-did the missing presentations the next day and shared the full presentation with everyone registered for the session. A full and uninterrupted version of the webinar has since been available online⁷.

2.7 Scientific publications

Due to confidentiality issues, partners have replaced, in some cases, scientific publications by other dissemination activities to promote their findings and scientific publications are still underway from the CIRC-PACK consortium. A large part of the deliverables in the CIRC-PACK project were confidential and work carried out carries intellectual property rights for European companies. At present, several knowledge partners are still exploring papers related to the CIRC-PACK project. CIRCE is ready to publish the paper *“Social Life Cycle Assessment of product value chains under a circular economy approach: A case study in the plastic packaging sector”* in Sustainability Journal as an open access publication before the end of the project. EKODENGE has submitted a paper entitled *“Addressing the gap to achieve plastics circularity in Europe”* to Environment Journal, which is under review, and a paper entitled *“Prospective evaluation of circular economy practices within plastic packaging value chain through optimization of life cycle impacts and circularity”*, which is also under review with the Sustainability Journal.

Other dissemination activities have been done to share the highly technical results of CIRC-PACK with a scientific and industrial audience, for example, through the active contribution from the Dutch Partner BUMAGA, to a report on the Paper and Board Industry in the Netherlands heavily influenced by CIRC-PACK lessons or sharing the results at several conferences.

2.8 Media and press releases

CIRC-PACK partners began media work when the project started, and have since kept it going, albeit at different intensity level both between periods and between partners. In total, through the monitoring tool, partners have reported 7 press releases shared, 20 media articles and 60 web articles.

⁷ The full CIRC-PACK final webinar online: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u1nOINKp4NU>

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Media activities reported by partners: 89

Figure 5: Partners have reported 89 media activities with a majority registered as web articles.

This number of media articles is above the adjusted KPIs and is satisfactory especially as the final year of the project resulted in more than 20 media mentions, and thus surpassed even the original KPI. The number of web articles – which in most cases are activities published on the CIRC-PACK website or partner websites – illustrates the effort made, while the reported number of press releases is also above project KPIs.

Examples of published media products include:

- Euronews (May 2019): Euronews TV feature on CIRC-PACK project:
<https://www.euronews.com/2019/05/27/how-companies-across-europe-are-creating-sustainable-products-using-less-water-and-less-en>
- Bioplastic News (December 2019): CIRC-Pack Tested Bioplastics Packaging
<https://bioplasticsnews.com/2019/12/10/circ-pack-tested-bioplastics-packaging/>
- Innovators Magazine (January 2020): Planetary love goes full circle
<https://www.innovatorsmag.com/love-goes-full-circle/>

The final press release during the CIRC-PACK project was sent out in late May and was published by Recycling Magazine and Recycling International, among others, within the first couple of days.

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Picture 8: Screenshot from two publishers sharing the final CIRC-PACK press release

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2.9 Project videos

The videos produced in CIRC-PACK includes two overall project videos and four videos from the partner OCU. In addition, some events have also been shared in a recorded version.

The number of total views of the videos, at this time being more than 3,000, indicates that the videos have been shared widely reaching a big audience.

It is expected that the videos will continue to have an impact after project's ending and will help remind the public about the work done in Europe to make the plastics industry circular through Horizon 2020.

For more information on the videos produced in CIRC-PACK, please read deliverable 8.3 on the videos produced in CIRC-PACK.

Picture 9: Screenshot from the final CIRC-PACK video

2.10 Partner Channels

As the numbers for web articles in section 2.8 shows, the partners have used their own channels to disseminate content. The technical and industrial partners have shared some, albeit limited, news online but has been heavily engaged in disseminating content through professional networks at events and in other meetings. For the public, especially OCU – a consumer association – has shared a number of articles with its large network of consumers and other interest organisations with a combined membership of more than 1 million consumers.

ICLEI Europe has published articles when relevant news were available for its large city network and Plastipolis has shared relevant events, etc. with its network in the plastics industry.

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3 CHALLENGES AND KEY LESSONS LEARNT

Throughout the CIRC-PACK project a number of challenges were identified and dealt with to successfully communicate the results of the project. The three main challenges, and the measures taken to address these challenges are described below.

3.1 Results from projects come in late in the project timeline

In a highly sophisticated project such as CIRC-PACK, the final and combined results of all the activities from partners come to full fruition late in the process. This is only natural, but relevant to always keep in mind when planning a communication process. In CIRC-PACK, this was addressed in a number of ways, the most significant being:

- **Continuous knowledge-exchange and sharing of preliminary results** from partners through attendance at events, news stories on the CIRC-PACK website and discussions in professional forums. CIRC-PACK partners reported taking part in more than 130 events throughout the project and managed to share the preliminary results in that way.
- **CIRC-PACK always planned for a late sharing of the final results of the project, through a dedicated final event, final press release, a final brochure and a final video.** The products combined allowed everyone to learn from the accumulated lessons from CIRC-PACK once they were drawn.
- **Project website and partner dedication will outlive the project, and hence the results of the CIRC-PACK project will continue to be shared.** With public deliverables available on the website – and the EU CORDIS portal – CIRC-PACK work will inspire other professionals in the sector in the years ahead. The final results of demo cases as well as the CIRCE Eco-design tool were also shared through the [Horizon Results Platform](#) which will make it easily findable for anyone interested in plastics circularity projects and their results.

3.2 The European Circularity “sector” is both large and diverse

The plastics industry, green NGOs, scientific institutions, government officials at both local and international level, consumer organisations and many other stakeholders all matter for a project such as CIRC-PACK and can all benefit from learning about the project. In total, this includes last and vastly different target groups, and must be prioritized when communicating about a project. CIRC-PACK did this in a number of ways:

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- First and foremost, CIRC-PACK took this into account in the very first edition of the CDP Plan (Deliverable 8.1) and **clearly mapped the many different target groups** (see Section 1.2.2. of this document) of interest to the consortium. Individual messages were developed for each type of target audience and made available for partners to use in their communication efforts.
- **Different channels for different target groups** is another way to overcome the challenge of having a very diverse group of potential stakeholders. In CIRC-PACK, the consortium was well positioned to reach out through various channels, for example through the membership magazines of the consumer organisation OCU, industry trade shows, city magazines or with videos addressing both the general audience and serving as a first peek for experts.
- Finally, **CIRC-PACK joined with other projects in the Plastics Circularity Multiplier initiative** helping the project to address a wider group of people working with circular plastics. This was useful in securing the specific audience interested in circularity in relations to packaging was reached.

3.3 Industrial partners must also ensure confidentially and intellectual rights

While all partners in CIRC-PACK agreed on and supported the important work to share the results of the project, some consideration for IPRs and confidential information must be taken in highly innovative – and industry supported – projects. In CIRC-PACK, for example, only 16 out of 52 deliverables from the project were public deliverables while rest were confidential. This balance was addressed in the communications work in the following ways:

- **Engage with partners and share materials in other ways than with publication of deliverables.** Keep the dialogue open on what can be published and what should remain internal knowledge. In CIRC-PACK this was especially essential with the Demo Cases (Work Packages 3, 4 and 5) where all deliverables were confidential, but CIRC-PACK nonetheless shared factsheets, videos etc. due to close partnership between the communications work package and the respective WP leaders.
- **Publish what can be published** and ensure interested parties can find information and contact partners through the website and meet them at events. By the end of the CIRC-PACK project, all public deliverables are available on the website, and the CIRC-PACK email will be continuously monitored by ICLEI.
- Respect the wish of confidentiality while working on producing the needed public dissemination materials. In CIRC-PACK this has been most impactful in the publication of scientific articles, which will be an ongoing issue even after the project ends. Close dialogue is needed to ensure generated knowledge is shared and one alternative, and a measure that can help do so, is to publish other highly technical

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material than scientific publications as such. For example, CIRC-PACK partner BUMAGA published a report on recycling of paper and board in the Netherlands heavily influenced by their work in CIRC-PACK and available for specialists to benefit from.

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4 CONCLUSIONS

The overall conclusion of the communications activities in the CIRC-PACK project is that partners successfully shared the innovative work done by partners to help improve the circularity of packaging. To clarify how, it is worth taking a second look at the KPIs presented in the original Communications and Dissemination Plan and compare it to the achieved results.

Table 2: Results compared to Communication and Dissemination indicators for evaluation as seen in the updated CDP from M24. "5 press mentions per year" was an adjustment in the updated CDP down from an original target of 20.

Results compared to Communication and Dissemination indicators for evaluation						
	Website	Newsletter	Social media	Videos	Events	Media actions
KPI's	2.000 unique visitors over the course of the project	200 subscribers	200 total followers for Twitter and LinkedIn	1.000 total views	20 participants in each workshop and 50 in final conference	5 press releases in total, and at least 5 press mentions per year
Results	15.000 visitors in the final year alone.	Goal reached with final email sending.	Over 1.800 followers on Twitter. 340 members on LinkedIn	More than 3.000 total views.	Several workshops with more than 20 participants and 116 participants in final conference online.	No less than 7 PR's were published in the Project and 20 Media mentions were achieved in the last year.

As described in this report, the CIRC-PACK project massively overachieved on a wide range of the KPIs most notably on the website, on the total views of videos and on Twitter/LinkedIn followers. The final physical event was also scheduled to have been attended by much more than 50 participants, and the KPI was more than doubled in the online version and the workshops were well attended. The KPI for subscribers to the newsletter was reached in terms of how many mailings were sent out with the final CIRC-PACK information. The KPI for press releases was also surpassed and the adapted KPI for press mentions the same. In addition, the final year – with the results being in from the project – also led to more than 20 press mentions as sought in the original KPI. The KPI for subscribers to the newsletter was reached in terms of how many mailings were sent out with the final CIRC-PACK information.

The story of the CIRC-PACK project has been told but will continue to stay alive online and through the partners' work as ambassadors for the results.